

Planetary Sapience and Speculative Visions of Search Engines

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1. Abstract

The poster will explore speculative visions and scenarios that revolve around the access and availability of information in relation to subjectivity, governance, and the environment. With technology often being anticipated by philosophy, artistic visions, or political utopias, the poster will be an invitation to think about the future of search engines and their role in society (see e.g., Haqq-Misra, Profitiliotis, & Kopparapu, 2024; Engerman, 2012; Parisi, 2012).

Self-awareness and self-determination are shaped by what information we have available, information which in turn needs to be created, compiled, and interpreted. Realizing we live on a planet that orbits the sun was based on the availability of a range of measurements, including the movements of the stars and planets on the night sky and of the geography of our planet. Similarly, social and economic data like GDP, suicide rates, poverty, housing conditions, and crime rates have not only fueled new social movements and new forms of political and economic coordination, but also affected individuals' meaning-making around their own selves (Zizek, 2005). In our present day, the very discovery of many environmental problems, including climate change, has rested on data from thermometers, satellites, ice drill samples, and so forth, being a pre-condition for climate awareness and action (Bratton, 2016, 2019; Edwards, 2013).

Access to information is thus connected to the self-awareness, identity, and sovereignty of humanity and its potential to govern its environment, something that has also inspired various utopian and dystopian visions. Paul Otlet's utopian project of the Mundaneum (Rayward, 2017) or the Noosphere of Russian Cosmism (Young, 2012) are early examples of visions of the future where information access is connected to increasing knowledge and self-awareness of humanity, with modern counterparts found for example in Bratton's vision of planetary-scale computation, terraforming, and planetary sapience (Bratton, 2016, 2019, 2021).

The process of making the poster will include making an inventory and selection of speculative visions from different fields like philosophy, art and politics. This could, for example, include visions from sci-fi like Isaac Asimov's Multivac computer (Asimov, 2016), Stanisław Lem's ariadnology (Lem, 2013), Liu Cixin's AI in Three Body Problem (Liu, 2014), and so forth (e.g. Lee & Quifan, 2024; Robinson, 2020). The poster can also draw from recent explorations of similar topics in the artistic field, including Suzanne Triester's Hexen (Treister & Bang, 2012), the Atlas of Anomalous AI (2020), and similar works.

2. Acknowledgements

Funding by The Swedish Foundation for Strategic Environmental Research via Mistra Environmental Communication.

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SEASON 2025, September 24–25, 2025, Hamburg, Germany

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17156187>

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